

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE EFFECT OF BINDING CLAYS ON GAS PERMEABILITY OF SAND-CLAY MOLD MIXTURES

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Abstract: This research examines the influence of varying amounts of binder clays on the gas permeability of sand-clay molds. The studies primarily focused on preparing mold compounds for low alloy steel casting. Additionally, a mathematical model was developed to describe the effect of binding clays on the gas permeability of the sand-clay molds.

Keywords: Bentonite, kaolin, gas permeability, sand-clay mold, compressive binding strength, mathematical model, Lagrange.

Introduction.

To achieve high-quality cast products, it is essential to consider not only the optimal melting methods of the alloy but also several other factors. These include the quality of the molds, the composition of the sand-clay mold mixture, its specified properties, the geometry of the alloy placement in the mold, and the correct selection and calculation of the casting systems [1-5].

Ensuring that the mold cavity does not deform during the pouring of liquid metal into the sand-clay mold is crucial. This requires the use of binding materials that provide sufficient strength to the quartz sand in the mold. The primary binders used are clays, including kaolin, halloysite, hydromica, montmorillonite, polygorskite, vermiculite, and allophane. Montmorillonite, which contains bentonite, is commonly used as a binder for one-time molding compounds. Additionally, it is important to note that an increase in the sand's moisture content leads to a decrease in gas permeability [6-9].

Material and methods.

Testing the gas permeability capability is crucial. The air present in the mold mixture and the gases generated during casting must escape easily during the pouring of the liquid metal. If not, they will reduce the mechanical properties of the cast product and decrease the fluidity of the liquid metal.

Figure 1 shows the gas permeability values of the sand-clay mold mixture. High gas permeability was observed in the mold mixture bonded with bentonite clay, specifically for 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8% binder clay additions, with values of 64, 60, 57, 40, and 27 cm³/kg min, respectively. In contrast, the mold mixture bonded with kaolin clay at the same 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8% binder clay additions had gas permeability values of 53, 45, 34, 28, and 13 cm³/kg min, respectively. Another important aspect is that the gas permeability of the sand-clay mold mixture decreases as the amount of binder clay additions increases [10-12].

Fig. 1. Gas permeability values of the sand-clay mold mixture with different amounts of kaolin and bentonite binding clays.

Research results indicate that bentonite binding clays have lower compressive binding strength compared to kaolin binding clays, but they offer higher gas permeability. Since the molds we use for casting shaft parts do not require high-precision geometric dimensions or thin-walled sections, the compressive binding strength of the mold mixture with bentonite binding clays is adequate. Due to the gas porosity observed in the analyzed defects, it is essential for our mold mixture to have high gas permeability [13, 14].

Given that the experiments utilized two types of binding clays, we will derive mathematical expressions for the gas permeability of the mold mixture for each type.

Results.

Initially, we will create a mathematical model to describe the relationship between the gas permeability of the sand-clay mold mixture and varying amounts of kaolin clay. By treating the amount of kaolin binding clay as a variable, we will address the problem of forming a function that represents the gas permeability of the sand-clay mold mixture. This involves constructing the Lagrange interpolation polynomial, thereby reducing the problem to a system of algebraic equations. By determining the unknown coefficients, we can express the gas permeability function in polynomial form.

y – amount of gas permeability, $cm^3/kg\ min$;

x – amount of kaolin binding clay, in %;

$$y = f(x); \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} 4^5 x_1 + 4^4 x_2 + \dots + 4x = 53 \\ 5^5 x_1 + 5^4 x_2 + \dots + 5x = 45 \\ 6^5 x_1 + 6^4 x_2 + \dots + 6x = 34 ; \quad (2) \\ 7^5 x_1 + 7^4 x_2 + \dots + 7x = 28 \\ 8^5 x_1 + 8^4 x_2 + \dots + 8x = 13 \end{cases}$$

$$x_1 = -0.03$$

$$x_3 = -1.64$$

$$x_5 = 49.83$$

$$x_2 = 0.48$$

$$x_4 = -8.3$$

(2) We can convert the system of equations into matrix form and solve for the unknowns using Cramer’s method for complex linear equations. First, we find the determinant Δ of the matrix formed by the system of equations.

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} 1024 & 256 & 64 & 16 & 4 \\ 15625 & 3125 & 625 & 25 & 5 \\ 7776 & 1296 & 216 & 36 & 6 \\ 16807 & 2401 & 343 & 49 & 7 \\ 32768 & 4096 & 512 & 64 & 8 \end{vmatrix} = -4191344640 \quad (3)$$

solving the above matrices, we find the following values of the unknowns,

$$x_1 = \frac{\Delta_1}{\Delta} = \frac{125412000}{-4191344640} = -\frac{37325}{1247424}; \quad x_2 = \frac{\Delta_2}{\Delta} = \frac{-2021974080}{-4191344640} = \frac{300889}{623712};$$

$$x_3 = \frac{\Delta_3}{\Delta} = \frac{6949350240}{-4191344640} = -\frac{2068259}{1247424}; \quad x_4 = \frac{\Delta_4}{\Delta} = \frac{34854469440}{-4191344640} = -\frac{5186677}{673712};$$

$$x_5 = \frac{\Delta_5}{\Delta} = \frac{-208841928960}{-4191344640} = \frac{7769417}{155928};$$

Once the equations are solved and the unknowns are determined, the function that represents the gas permeability of the sand-clay mold mixture based on the amount of kaolin binding clay is as follows:

$$y = -0.03x^5 + 0.48x^4 - 1.64x^3 - 8.3x^2 + 49.83x; \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2. Mathematical model based on research results correspondence to actual results

Next, we will develop a mathematical model to describe how the gas permeability of a mold mixture depends on varying amounts of bentonite binding clay in the sand-clay mixture. By treating the amount of bentonite binding clay as a variable, we aim to create a function that represents the gas permeability of the mixture. To achieve this, we will construct a Lagrange interpolation polynomial. This approach reduces the problem to a system of algebraic equations, allowing us to determine the unknown coefficients and express the gas permeability function in polynomial form.

y – amount of gas permeability, cm³/kg min;

x – amount of bentonite binding clay, in %;

$$y = f(x); \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{cases} 4^5 x_1 + 4^4 x_2 + \dots + 4x = 64 \\ 5^5 x_1 + 5^4 x_2 + \dots + 5x = 60 \\ 6^5 x_1 + 6^4 x_2 + \dots + 6x = 57; \quad (6) \\ 7^5 x_1 + 7^4 x_2 + \dots + 7x = 40 \\ 8^5 x_1 + 8^4 x_2 + \dots + 8x = 27 \end{cases}$$

$$x_1 = 0.022$$

$$x_3 = 1.04$$

$$x_5 = 17.25$$

$$x_2 = -0.32$$

$$x_4 = -0.9$$

(6) We can convert the system of equations into matrix form and solve for the unknowns using Cramer’s method for complex linear equations. First, we find the determinant Δ of the matrix

formed by the system of equations.

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} 1024 & 256 & 64 & 16 & 4 \\ 15625 & 3125 & 625 & 25 & 5 \\ 7776 & 1296 & 216 & 36 & 6 \\ 16807 & 2401 & 343 & 49 & 7 \\ 32768 & 4096 & 512 & 64 & 8 \end{vmatrix} = -4191344640 \quad (7)$$

solving the above matrices, we find the following values of the unknowns,

$$x_1 = \frac{\Delta_1}{\Delta} = \frac{-92579040}{-4191344640} = \frac{64291}{2910656}; \quad x_2 = \frac{\Delta_2}{\Delta} = \frac{1369552320}{-4191344640} = -\frac{475539}{1455328};$$

$$x_3 = \frac{\Delta_3}{\Delta} = \frac{-4481022240}{-4191344640} = \frac{3111821}{2910656}; \quad x_4 = \frac{\Delta_4}{\Delta} = \frac{2487216960}{-4191344640} = -\frac{863617}{1455328};$$

$$x_5 = \frac{\Delta_5}{\Delta} = \frac{-69265140480}{-4191344640} = \frac{6012599}{363832};$$

Once the equations are solved and the unknowns are determined, the function that represents the gas permeability of the sand-clay mold mixture based on the amount of bentonite binding clay is as follows:

$$y = 0.022x^5 - 0.32x^4 + 1.04x^3 - 0.9x^2 + 17.52x; \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3. Mathematical model based on research results correspondence to actual results

Conclusion.

This research analyzes the effect of varying amounts of binder clays in sand-clay mold mixtures. A mathematical model was developed to describe the influence of binding clays on the gas permeability of these molds. This model enables further research without the need for experimental results.

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